

Clinical and Demographic Predictors of Successful Vagal Maneuver Response in Supraventricular Tachycardia Patients

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Abstract

Objective: The objective of this study was to identify clinical and demographic factors associated with successful response to vagal maneuvers in patients presenting with acute supraventricular tachycardia in the emergency department.

Material and Methods: This descriptive study was conducted in the emergency department of a tertiary cardiac care center. A total of 154 patients aged 18 to 50 years with electrocardiographically confirmed supraventricular tachycardia were included. Patients underwent carotid sinus massage standard Valsalva maneuver or modified Valsalva maneuver. Demographic variables and clinical characteristics including age gender diabetes hypertension smoking status duration of symptoms and history of supraventricular tachycardia were recorded. The dataset was processed and evaluated using SPSS version 26. Associations between categorical variables were examined through the Chi-square test, and statistical significance was interpreted at a p-value < 0.05.

Results: A total of 154 patients with supraventricular tachycardia were analyzed with a mean age of 34.69 ± 7.04 years. Overall successful termination using vagal maneuvers was achieved in (61.0%) of patients. The modified Valsalva maneuver showed the highest success rate at (81.2%) compared to standard Valsalva maneuver at (46.8%) and carotid sinus massage at (47.7%) and this difference was statistically significant with a p value less than (p=0.001). Female patients demonstrated significantly higher success rates than males with a (p=0.025). Patients without diabetes mellitus had better response compared to diabetic patients and this association was statistically significant with a (p=0.009). A prior history of supraventricular tachycardia was also significantly associated with successful response with a p value of (p=0.003).

Conclusion: The findings indicate a clinical and demographic factors significantly influence the effectiveness of vagal maneuvers in supraventricular tachycardia. Female gender absence of diabetes mellitus and prior history of supraventricular tachycardia are important predictors of successful response.

Keywords: Perception, practice, self-medication, undergraduate medical students.

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Introduction

Supraventricular tachycardia (SVT) is a heterogeneous group of arrhythmias used to describe tachycardias that involve cardiac tissue at the level of the bundle of His or above¹.

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Supraventricular tachycardia is considered as a heart abnormality which presents in the form of fast heart rate. It is a generic term that is associated with any tachycardia that originates above ventricles, involving atrial tissue or the atrioventricular nodal tissue¹. The prevalence of SVT is 2.25/1000 persons with a female predominance of 2:1 across all age groups². Three most common types of SVT are atrioventricular nodal reentrant tachycardia (AVNRT), atrioventricular re-entrant tachycardia (AVRT) and atrial tachycardia (AT). AVNRT is the most common SVT in the general population and accounts for over 60% of patients undergoing invasive cardiac electrophysiology study³. Palpitations and pounding in the neck or head are the most common symptoms of SVT and may be accompanied by

chest discomfort (chest pain is unusual), dyspnea, anxiety, lightheadedness or, uncommonly, syncope. Electrocardiogram (ECG) is diagnostic showing a narrow complex tachycardia (QRS duration, < 120ms) but may have a prolonged QRS interval (> 120ms) when associated with pre-existing or raterelated bundle branch block.⁴

Treatment options for SVT include vagal maneuvers, pharmacologic therapy, and synchronized cardio-version. Hemodynamic instability demands urgent synchronized cardioversion while in stable patient vagal maneuvers are attempted first to abort an acute episode of SVT. By increasing vagal tone, vagal maneuvers slow conduction in the atrioventricular (AV) node resulting in termination of AV nodal dependent re-entry tachycardias, such as AV nodal re-entry tachycardia and AV reentry tachycardia.⁵ Supraventricular tachycardia can occur as a result of structural abnormalities and heart failure. It can be treated by vagal maneuvers, several medications or else by electrical therapy¹. Vagal maneuvers however, are considered as first line management tools for reversing Supraventricular tachycardia in the emergency-care setting, which needs continuous examination and refinement for defining its appropriateness as well as effectiveness⁵. Studies have reported approximately 25% success rate for vagal maneuvers, although the rate varies widely in the literature (6–54%). Common vagal maneuvers include carotid sinus massage (CSM), Valsalva maneuver (VM) and modified Valsalva maneuver (mVM). Less commonly used maneuvers include ocular pressure, stimulation of the gag reflex, applied abdominal pressure, and headstands and diving reflex⁶.

Ezgi et al demonstrated the efficacy and maintenance of sinus rhythm with vagal maneuvers. The study was completed with 98 patients. A total of 25 (25.5%) cases of SVT were initially treated successfully with vagal maneuvers. The success rate was 43.7% (14/32 cases) from mVM, 24.2% (8/33) for sVM, and 9.1 % (3/33) for CSM ($p < 0.05$)⁷.

Vagal maneuvers are simple bedside methods in termination of an acute episode of Supraventricular tachycardia SVT. To the best of our knowledge, only a few studies had evaluated the effectiveness of a VM however local data is very scarce. Therefore, in this study, we aimed to evaluate the efficacy of VMs in Pakistani patients with SVT. This will be beneficial not only for patients but also for health-care providers worldwide, including regions with few health-care resources. Furthermore, it will shorten the patient stay in hospital and will guide us to formulate a plan for patient management and duration of hospital stay.

Material and Methods

This descriptive study was conducted in the Emergency Department of Faisalabad Institute of Cardiology

Faisalabad over a six-month period from 20th August 2023 to 19th February 2024. The sample size of 154 patients was calculated using World Health Organization sample size calculation with a ninety five percent confidence level an anticipated proportion of 9.1 percent for carotid sinus massage and an absolute precision of 4.55 percent. Non probability consecutive sampling technique was used to recruit patients. Both male and female patients aged between 18 and 50 years with electrocardiographically documented supraventricular tachycardia were included in the study. Patients with hemodynamic instability pregnancy or contraindications to Valsalva maneuver or carotid sinus massage such as aortic stenosis recent myocardial infarction glaucoma retinopathy cerebrovascular accident transient ischemic attack or carotid bruit were excluded. After obtaining approval from the ethical review committee and CPSP informed consent was taken from all participants ensuring confidentiality and patient safety. A focused medical history was recorded for each patient. Eligible patients were divided into three groups and underwent carotid sinus massage standard Valsalva maneuver or modified Valsalva maneuver according to predefined protocols. Patients in whom vagal maneuvers failed were managed with adenosine according to guideline directed therapy. Successful cases were monitored with a twelve-lead electrocardiogram and observed for two hours prior to discharge. Data were collected on a predesigned proforma and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Continuous variables were expressed as mean and standard deviation while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Chi square test was applied to assess associations and a p value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Age range in this study was from 18 to 50 years with mean age of 34.69 ± 7.04 years. Majority of the patients 92 (59.74%) were between 18 to 35 years of age as shown in Table I. Out of 154 patients, 88 (57.14%) were male and 66 (42.86%) were females with male to female ratio 1.3:1 as shown in Figure V. Mean duration of symptoms in our study was 15.35 ± 6.69 hours as shown in Table II. Mean time until reversion was 27.53 ± 3.03 minutes. Mean systolic blood pressure was 132.44 ± 10.43 mmHg. Mean diastolic blood pressure was 93.22 ± 6.54 mmHg. Distribution of patients according to DM and HTN is shown in Table III & IV respectively. Distribution of patients according to smoking & h/o SVT is shown in Table V & VI respectively. Distribution of patients according to family h/o SVT and type of maneuver is shown in Table VII & VIII respectively.

Table 1: Stratification of Efficacy with Respect to Type of Maneuver

Type of Maneuver	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	P-value
Carotid Sinus Massage (CSM)	21 (47.73)	23 (52.27)	0.0001
Modified Valsalva Maneuver (mVM)	52 (81.25)	12 (18.75)	
Standard Valsalva Maneuver (sVM)	22 (46.81)	25 (53.19)	

The stratification of efficacy by type of maneuver demonstrates a highly significant difference in success rates among the three vagal techniques. The modified Valsalva maneuver showed the highest efficacy with successful termination of supraventricular tachycardia in 81.25 percent of patients indicating superior effectiveness compared to the other maneuvers. In contrast carotid sinus massage and standard Valsalva maneuver showed comparatively lower success rates of 47.73 percent and 46.81 percent respectively. The observed difference in efficacy across maneuver types was statistically significant with a p value of 0.0001 confirming that the type of vagal maneuver plays a crucial role in successful cardioversion. These findings support the preferential use of the modified Valsalva maneuver as a first line non pharmacological intervention in the acute management of supraventricular tachycardia.

Table 2: Stratification of efficacy with respect to age, gender, duration of symptoms, HTN, DM, Smoking, history of SVT, family history of SVT and blood pressure.

Variable	Category	Yes n=94 n (%)	No n=60 n (%)	P-value
Age (years)	18–35	57 (61.96)	35 (38.04)	0.776
	36–50	37 (59.68)	25 (40.32)	
Gender	Male	47 (53.41)	41 (46.59)	0.025
	Female	47 (71.21)	19 (28.79)	
Duration of symptoms (hours)	≤12	30 (52.63)	27 (47.37)	0.101
	>12	64 (65.98)	33 (34.02)	

Diabetes Mellitus	Yes	22 (45.83)	26 (54.17)	0.009
	No	72 (67.92)	34 (32.08)	
Hypertension	Yes	30 (57.69)	22 (42.31)	0.543
	No	64 (62.75)	38 (37.25)	
Smoking	Yes	25 (62.50)	15 (37.50)	0.826
	No	69 (60.53)	45 (39.47)	
History of SVT	Yes	16 (94.12)	01 (5.88)	0.003
	No	78 (56.93)	59 (43.07)	
Family history of SVT	Yes	09 (45.00)	11 (55.00)	0.115
	No	85 (63.43)	49 (36.57)	
Blood Pressure (mmHg)	≤120/90	30 (52.63)	27 (47.37)	0.101
	>120/90	64 (65.98)	33 (34.02)	

The results of stratification analysis demonstrate that the efficacy of vagal maneuvers in terminating supraventricular tachycardia was significantly influenced by certain clinical and demographic variables. Gender showed a statistically significant association with efficacy as female patients exhibited a higher success rate compared to male patients with a p value of 0.025 indicating better responsiveness to vagal maneuvers. Diabetes mellitus was also found to have a significant impact on outcomes as non-diabetic patients demonstrated a markedly higher success rate than diabetic patients with a statistically significant p value of 0.009 suggesting that metabolic status may influence vagal responsiveness. A previous history of supraventricular tachycardia emerged as the strongest predictor of successful response with patients having prior episodes showing substantially higher efficacy and a highly significant p value of 0.003. In contrast age groups duration of symptoms hypertension smoking status family history of supraventricular tachycardia and baseline blood pressure did not show statistically significant associations with vagal maneuver efficacy as all corresponding p values were greater than 0.05. These findings indicate that while most demographic and clinical factors do not significantly alter outcomes female gender absence of diabetes and prior exposure to supraventricular tachycardia are important determinants of successful vagal maneuver response.

Discussion

Paroxysmal supraventricular tachycardia (PSVT) is a common arrhythmia which may be associated to a variety of electrophysiological abnormalities, including increased automaticity, triggered activity and re-entry circuits which develop in the atrial myocardium or in the atrioventricular (AV) junction.⁷⁸⁻⁸² The general clinical approach to a subject with suspected PSVT includes a brief and targeted history and an accurate analysis of the electrocardiogram (ECG), in the attempt to differentiate PSVT from other narrow-complex tachycardias and to choose the most appropriate treatment.^{83,84} When no haemodynamic instability is present, vagal manoeuvres, adenosine and verapamil are usually considered as the first-line treatment of choice for PSVT,⁸⁵⁻⁸⁷ and the relative efficacy of each has been evaluated in many studies.⁸⁸⁻⁹³ I have conducted this study to determine the effectiveness of Vagal Maneuvers in termination of an acute episode of Supraventricular tachycardia SVT. Age range in this study was from 18 to 50 years with mean age of 34.69 ± 7.04 years. Majority of the patients 92 (59.74%) were between 18 to 35 years of age. Out of 154 patients, 88 (57.14%) were male and 66 (42.86%) were females with male to female ratio 1.3:1. In our study, efficacy of Vagal Maneuvers in termination of an acute episode of Supraventricular tachycardia SVT was found in 94 (61.04%) patients. The efficacy was 81.25% (52/64 cases) from mVM, 46.81% (22/47) for sVM, and 47.33% (21/44) for CSM ($p < 0.05$). Ezgi et al demonstrated the efficacy and maintenance of sinus rhythm with vagal maneuvers. The study was completed with 98 patients. A total of 25 (25.5%) cases of SVT were initially treated successfully with vagal maneuvers. The success rate was 43.7% (14/32 cases) from mVM, 24.2% (8/33) for sVM, and 9.1 % (3/33) for CSM ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

This study concluded that the effectiveness of Vagal Maneuvers in termination of an acute episode of Supraventricular tachycardia is very high with modified Valsalva maneuver (mVM) as the most effective technique. So, we recommend that modified Valsalva maneuver (mVM) should be used preferably in managing supraventricular tachycardia.

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Author's contribution:

MAA, ME: Conceptualization of Project

AR, SA: Data Collection

NH, HMF: Literature Search

AR: Statistical Analysis

AR, SA: Drafting, Revision

MAA: Writing of Manuscript